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Literacy Rate in Rural Muslims of Jalgaon District of Maharashtra: A Geographical Study

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Abstract:

India is a fast-growing nation in the world, but the overall educational situation of the Indian population, particularly the Muslim population, is not very good in condition on these days. Indian literacy has seen significant progress over the years. As of the latest data, the literacy rate in India is around 77%, with variations between urban and rural areas, as well as among different states and demographics.

The government has implemented several policies, initiatives regarding to improve literacy rate, educational structure, such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) and the National Literacy Mission. Despite these efforts, challenges remain, including socio-economic factors, gender disparities, and access to quality education. The Muslim community was behind the majority of Indian communities and lacked access to modern education as time went on. The Muslim community in India has a low level of socioeconomic development due to a lack of higher education (technical and professional education) and a low level of basic education.

According to essential information gathered in the country areas of Jalgaon Locale, education rate among Muslims was 70.79%. It was 67.38 percent for Muslim women and 73.92 percent for Muslim men. In country areas of Jalgaon region likewise the situation of training among Muslim isn't great. Muslim females have a significantly higher rate of seventh-grade dropout than Muslim males do. However, after tenth standard by and large dropout rate increments around 95%.

Key Words: Literacy, Education, Dropout Rate, Religion, Socio-Economic Development,

Introduction:

Indian literacy has seen significant progress over the years. As of the latest data, the literacy rate in India is around 77%, with variations between urban and rural areas, as well as among different states and demographics. The government has implemented various initiatives to improve literacy, such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) and the National Literacy Mission. Despite these efforts, challenges remain, including socio-economic factors, gender disparities, and access to quality education. India is a country of diversity.

The diversity is in various caste, customs, culture, tradition, religions, etc. in the process of socio-economic development some sections of Indian society has matched the momentum of this development and some sections of society are in the phase of transition. Irrespective of caste, creed, culture, religion, etc. shown the different level of socio-economic development in various communities of India. Literacy and Education is one of the important factors and parameter to measure the socio-economic development of any religion, caste and community.

The socioeconomic of India's Muslims was excellent prior to independence, but it significantly deteriorated after independence. Despite being India's largest minority community, Muslims lag behind in education, employment, political and judicial representation, economic conditions, social assimilation, and other areas. In the present research paper literacy rate among rural Muslim population has analyzed for Jalgaon district of Maharashtra.

Study Area:

Jalgaon District is situated in the Western part of Indian Peninsula and Northern side of Maharashtra State. Khandesh Region was separated into two areas in 1906, called West Khandesh and East Khandesh with central command at Dhule and Jalgaon District separately.

Dhule and Jalgaon became the names of the two districts after the Maharashtra State was established in 1960.

The gold market, banana production, cotton cultivation, and the emergence of a regional industrial and educational hub make the Jalgaon district world-famous. The staple crops of the district are Banana and Cotton.

Jalgaon District are located between the range of 20° and 21° North Latitude. And 74° 55' and 76° 28' East Longitude. Jalgaon district occupies 11765 Sq. km. area. Officially it has 15 Tahsils. As per Census 2001 it had 3679936 total population. Out of which Muslim population is 455288. This creates the 12.37% to the total population of the Jalgaon District. 96878627 is the total population of Maharashtra, out of which 10270485 population of Muslims in Maharashtra. The share of Muslim Population to total population of Maharashtra is 10.6%. The total population of India is 1,02,86,10,328 out of which total Muslim population of is 13,81,88,240, which is the 13.4% to the population of India.

Objective of the study:

The objective of this study is to analyze the Literacy Rate among Rural Muslims in Jalgaon District.

Research Methodology:

The essential information was gathered by house-to-house interview technique with the assistance of standard survey. The essential information was gathered by utilizing arbitrary testing strategy. Around 1293 Muslim families (8443 Total Population) were randomly surveyed in the rural areas of selected village of Jalgaon district. After assortment of essential information, it was tabulated, classified and accumulated then same has been addressed via cartographic techniques.

Result and Discussion:

A) Study of Households and Population among Rural Muslims in Jalgaon District:

In Jalgaon district the highest concentration of rural Muslim households was found in the tahsils of Jamner, Jalgaon and Parola that was 19.41%, 12.92% and 10.75% respectively.

Sr. No.	Tahsil	No. of HH	% of HH	Total Population	% of Male	% of Female
1	Chopda	47	3.63	309	54.05	45.95
2	Yawal	83	6.42	537	52.70	47.30
3	Raver	115	8.89	737	51.56	48.44
4	Muktainagar	56	4.33	341	54.84	45.16
5	Bodvad	43	3.33	257	52.14	47.86
6	Bhusawal	37	2.86	202	50.99	49.01
7	Jalgaon	167	12.92	1032	52.33	47.67
8	Erandol	69	5.34	436	51.61	48.39
9	Dharangaon	28	2.17	159	54.09	45.91
10	Amalner	41	3.17	231	51.95	48.05
11	Parola	31	2.4	206	51.94	48.06
12	Bhadgaon	58	4.49	352	52.27	47.73
13	Chalisgaon	128	9.9	786	52.67	47.33
14	Pachora	139	10.75	793	51.32	48.68
15	Jamner	251	19.41	2065	51.57	48.43
	Total	1293	100	8443	52.14	47.86

Field Survey 2013

And lowest was in the tahsils of Dharangaon (2.17), Parola (2.4%) and Bhusawal (2.86%). In Jalgaon district, out of 8443 total population surveyed the average rural Muslim male is 52.14%. The highest rural Muslim male, as compared to average of district, was in the tahsils of Muktainagar (54.84%), Dharangaon (54.09%) and Chopda (54.05%). And lowest was in Bhusawal (50.99%), Pachora (51.32%) and Raver (51.56%) tahsils. On the other hand out of 8443 total population surveyed the average rural Muslim female is 47.86%. The highest rural Muslim female, as compared to average of district, was in the tahsils of Bhusawal (49.01%), Pachora (48.68%) and Raver (48.44%). And lowest was in Chopda (45.95%), Dharangaon (45.91%) and Muktainagar (45.16%) tahsils.

B) Study of Literacy Rate among Rural Muslims in Jalgaon District

According to 2011 Census, literacy rate of Jalgaon district was 79.73%. Male literacy rate was 87.97, while female literacy rate was 70.92%. At District level, the literacy rate for male was substantially more as compared to female in both rural and urban areas. As per primary data collected (2013), literacy rate of Muslim population in rural areas of District was 70.79%. It was 73.92% for Muslim Male and 67.38% for Muslim Female. In Jalgaon district literacy rate among rural Muslim population is 70.79%. As compared to the average of district, the highest literacy rate among rural Muslim population was in the tahsils of Bhusawal (82.18%), Parola (78.16%) and Bhadgaon (78.13%). And lowest literacy rate was in Jamner (63.15%), Bodvad (64.20%) and Pachora (68.10%) tahsils.

Sr. No.	Tahsil	Total Population	Total Literacy Rate	Male Literacy Rate	Female Literacy Rate
1	Chopda	309	73.14	76.05	69.72
2	Yawal	537	76.54	75.27	77.95
3	Raver	737	77.20	77.11	77.31
4	Muktainagar	341	75.07	76.47	73.38
5	Bodvad	257	64.20	63.43	65.04
6	Bhusawal	202	82.18	80.58	83.84
7	Jalgaon	1032	70.45	74.81	65.65
8	Erandol	436	75.69	77.78	73.46
9	Dharangaon	159	74.84	74.42	75.34
10	Amalner	231	69.70	68.33	71.17
11	Parola	206	78.16	78.50	77.78
12	Bhadgaon	352	78.13	78.26	77.98
13	Chalisgaon	786	75.95	76.09	75.81
14	Pachora	793	68.10	72.73	63.21
15	Jamner	2065	61.69	70.05	52.80
	Total	8443	70.79	73.92	67.38

Field Survey 2013

In Jalgaon district, literacy rate among rural Muslim male is 73.92%. The highest literacy rate among rural Muslim male, as compared to average of district, was in the tahsils of Bhusawal (80.58%), Parola (78.50%) and Bhadgaon (78.26%). And lowest was in Bodvad (63.43%), Amalner (68.33%) and Jamner (71.46%) tahsils. On the other hand in Jalgaon district, literacy rate among rural Muslim female is 67.38. The highest literacy rate among rural Muslim female, as compared to the average of district, was in the tahsils of Bhusawal (83.84%), Bhadgaon (77.98%) and Yawal (77.95%). And lowest was in the tahsils of Jamner (54.30%), Pachora (63.21%) and Bodvad (65.04%).

Conclusion:

Indian literacy has seen significant progress over the years. As of the latest data, the literacy rate in India is around 77%, with variations between urban and rural areas, as well as among different states and demographics. The government has implemented various policies, initiatives regarding to improve literacy rate educational structure, such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) and the National Literacy Mission. Despite these efforts, challenges remain, including socio-economic factors, gender disparities, and access to quality education. This disparity can be attributed to various factors, including socio-economic conditions, access to quality education, and regional variations. Efforts are being made to improve literacy rates within the community through targeted educational programs and initiatives. Hence, hypothesis is proves that literacy rate among rural Muslim population is low in Jalgaon district. Muslim population constitutes significant portion of India’s population and if we dream about developed India as key player in the world, we cannot ignore the overall development of Muslims. Potentials of Muslim population as Human Resources are not yet explored for the betterment of India. Presently, if we ignore the literacy rate, socio economic and educational conditions of India’s Muslims, we will obstruct and harm the peace, development and dream of India as a Superpower.

References:

Journals :

1. Dr. Patil N. A. and Dr. Suryawanshi A. S. ‘Disparity in the Level of Literacy a Spatio Temporal Case Study of Jalgaon District Maharashtra State (2001-2011).

2. Dutta S., and Sivaramakrishnan L. (2013). Disparity in the Literacy Level among the Scheduled and Non-Scheduled Population: Indian Scenario in the 21st Century, *Transactions* 35(2): 185-200.
3. Mulimani, A. A. and Pujar, L. M. (2015). Spatial Disparity of Rural-Urban Literacy in Haveri District, *Research Directions* 3 (6): 1-10.
4. Sopher, D. E. (1980). Sex disparity in Indian literacy. In D. E. Sopher (Ed.), *An exploration of India: Geographical perspectives on society and culture*. New York: Cornell Press. 130-188.

Books :

1. Andre Beteille (1974) "Social Inequality", Penguin Books Ltd. England.
2. Hamm and R. & M. C. Callagh P.S. "Quantitative Techniques in Geography: Oxford University Press.

Reports:

1. Annual Report of Minority Affair Ministry, Government of India - 2010-11
2. Census of India 2001, Vol. V. General Population Tables.
3. Census 2011 Report, Government of India.
4. India 2013 Publication Division, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Government of India.
5. Prime Minister's new 15 points programme for the welfare of minority.
6. Political economical weekly magazine
7. R. Sachar Commission report.